

A Paradigm shift in Education Management for teachers to Upskill ICT skills and Adapt Learning Management System

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Abstract: Technology plays a very significant role in raising and developing the standards of instruction and facilitating communication, both of which advance students' knowledge and abilities. Learning is an ever evolving process that makes greater use of contemporary technologies. Teachers will find it easier to gather information for pupils and to explain the subject. Teachers can better adapt to the global demand for technology – based teaching and learning technique and equip themselves to replace the traditional teaching methods with the help of integration of information, communication and technology (ICT). The goal of this study is to identify the variables that affect teachers' willingness to include ICT into the classroom. This study focuses on the events of instructors, provides significant new information about the variables influencing teachers' attitude towards integrating ICT in the classrooms. Therefore, this study is helpful to the teachers and students to create technologies for e- learning, quality assurance and improvement. This study compares teachers who regularly use a practice of teaching system with those who do not, in order to determine how accepting they are of a learning management system LMS. The outcomes would also help to clarify the kind of learning environment that can be created when ICT is incorporated into the classroom. The results of this study focuses on how beneficial ICT integration is for both educators and learners. The findings also say that one of the most crucial and important element in the effectiveness of technology – based teaching and learning is the proficient setup of ICT resources and incorporation of ICT by educators.

Keywords: ICT Integration, Technology effectiveness, Active learning, Pedagogical practices, Learner centered.

Introduction:

In this era, the term technology plays an important and vital role in education. Education can be carried on both formal and informal ways at all levels. This is because in most countries technology has become the highway of information transmission. For almost two decades, teachers are trying to integrate information technology into school education because the use of computers and technology in school education can significantly increase the quality of teaching. Education is often associated with highly qualified teachers, but with ICT it would be more learner – centered. (Tusubira and Kyeyune, 2001).

ICT is a wide term which includes integration of communication device. Information technology and communication technology have moved and therefore their convergence has resulted in ICT (Dogra. 2005). ICT is an important feature of future development. Through the latest National education policy, the Ministry of Education understands the importance of the technology-based teaching and learning, and, integration of ICT into the classroom and curriculum.

Passive learning is the most popular type of education, in which, students typically take notes during lectures and the teacher uses a blackboard and traditional lecture style. Information and communication technology, however, lends support to the “active learning” approach. Students engage in deeper critical thinking and higher cognitive processes as a result of active learning. Technology integration has revitalized and changed the student outlook, fundamentally altering their outlook and performance. In 2007 Grabe says according to this framework, curriculums at schools and other educational establishments that seek to educate students for life in the information society, ought to take information and communication technologies into account. For this reason, schools continually make investments in ICT and urge educators to use technology into their lesson plans.

However, using technology to facilitate meaningful learning was difficult for many teachers. Therefore, the development of teachers’ knowledge and skills in the usage of technology in the classroom is an important topic for schools. A content knowledge framework for technology based pedagogy, conceptually introduced to find, how effectively technology can be linked to pedagogical practices in classrooms. (Mishra and Koehler, 2006).

Using computer-based communication in the classroom as a regular aspect of instruction is known as information, communication and technology (ICT) integration. Teachers are considered to be important contributors to the usage of ICT and a learning management system in the classroom, when it comes to educating pupils for the present digital age. ICT implementation is a continual process that completely supports information resources and teaching and learning, rather than occurring in a single step.

An educational strategy known as “active “ or “learner centered learning” places the student as the center of the process and makes use of technology to facilitate and improve learning. The teaching and learning process has changed, becoming more dynamic, engaging and efficient with the incorporation of fundamental ICT tools. With the use of these resources, educators may now offer individualized training and promote team work. This study looks at the current procedure for examining the use of ICT in education and determining the value of information and communication tools in the classroom. Based on an extensive study of the literature, it also looks at how ICT enhances pedagogical perspectives in teaching and helps learning and growth. Additionally, it was acknowledged that teachers’ capacity building and professional development initiatives also play a key role in improving the quality of teachers and improved education for students.

The adoption of ICT in teaching mostly means adopting technology in teaching and learning which is related to the use of educational tools in schools. Since students are technologically strong and learn better in a technology-based environment, the integration of ICT in schools, especially in the classroom, is important. The use of technology in teaching greatly affects the methodological aspects, where the integration of ICT leads to an effective learning with the support of ICT elements and components. Earle (2002) associated ICT integration with the concept of the whole, when all the elements of a system are combined into a whole. For example, using technology in the classroom must bring together two important elements of teaching and learning, content and pedagogy. Otherwise, if the students receive several websites or ICT tools (e.g. CD-ROM, multimedia, etc.) and the teacher does not integrate ICT into the teaching, then the outcome would not be effective and support the pedagogies. In addition, ICT provides help and free support to the teachers and students, where it requires effective learning using computers as learning tools, and integrating ICT into the curriculum.

Education is a continuous learning that creates a proactive environment for teaching and learning, not a one step learning. Young (2003). The results of the study would help the education and educational institutions to formulate policies to adopt the use of ICT in teaching and adoption of ICT by teachers.

In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the adoption of ICT skills by teachers, driven by the recognition of its potential to transform pedagogical practices and improve educational outcomes. The rapid advancements in technology have introduced a plethora of digital tools and resources that hold promise for creating interactive and engaging learning environments. Learning Management Systems (LMS) are one such technology that has gained widespread attention in the educational landscape.

LMS platforms offer educators a comprehensive suite of tools and functionalities to manage course content, facilitate communication and collaboration, assess student progress and provide personalized learning experiences. These systems have the potential to streamline administrative tasks, promote active learning and cater to diverse learning needs and preferences. However, the effective utilization of LMS relies heavily on teachers' ICT competencies and their willingness to embrace technology-enhanced pedagogies.

Research Overview and Literature Review:

In addition, factors hindering the implementation of ICT and the main obstacles are investigated, based on a comprehensive literature review, on what basis ICT supports learning, development and broadens the pedagogical aspect of teaching. Previous studies have shown that the integration of ICT into the classroom is often poorly accepted and implemented in the classrooms. ICT integration is not a one-step learning process, but it is a continual process of learning that provides teaching-learning environment Young, (2003).

Hermans, Tondeur, Van-Braak, and Valcke (2008) have identified three main stages for ICT to be highly valued and regarded by the teachers; integration, enhancement and complimentary. Even though many teachers know that integrating ICT into teaching can help

students learn, many are reluctant to adopt ICT into teaching Herw and Brush, (2007). The technology pedagogy, content knowledge framework was taken to understand how technology can be integrated into classroom teaching practices. Mishra and Koehler, (2006).

However, infrastructure and facility of ICT is then need to supply to the schools. A key factor in use of ICT is sufficient computer labs and ICT equipment. This is to ensure that subject teachers are easily access to ICT tools whenever needed Hennessy, Ruthven,& Brindley, (2005).

In the technology adoption literature, self – sufficiency has been understood as a general concept. Self - efficacy refers to how teachers perceive their ability to use and adopt technology-based pedagogical activities. Tondeur et al., (2020).

Self –efficacy is not related to a specific technique, but rather the general competence of teachers in the field of ICT. From a focused perspective, self-efficacy refers to teachers' beliefs about their ability to use a particular educational technology. Kemp et al., (2019).

Technology adoption is not a single process but occurs over time. Blau and Shamir Inbal, (2017). It is important to study acceptance of technology by focusing on users with different technical experience and acceptance. Several researchers have studied the level of, use of information and communication technology by educators and related factors.

The degree of ICT proficiency among teachers and the degree to which ICT has been incorporated into classroom instruction in vocational education and vocational schools have been evaluated by Jawarneh et al., (2007). According to the study's findings, professional teachers just need a basic understanding of ICT. Simson (2004) looked into how primary school teachers felt about using computers in the classroom using a quantitative method. The findings demonstrated how instructors' attitudes and beliefs affected, how they used ICT in the classroom. Moses (2006) looked at teaching techniques in another study involving 390 instructors and discovered that while nearly all of them were highly proficient in ICT, some even using it at a higher level, few teachers used ICT in the classroom. Teachers in 11 schools were polled by Rakes et al., (2006), who discovered that more than 25% of educators incorporate ICT into the classroom on a regular basis.

The teaching, pedagogical approach, the teacher's computer experience, and a positive attitude toward computers had a positive effect on the intensive use of ICT teachers, according to Drent and Meelissen's (2008), investigation into the factors that contributed to teachers' intensive use of ICT.

Kushkaya and Kocak (2010) conducted a study on how educators utilize educational technology and discovered that they primarily use it for administrative tasks rather than teaching. Lau and Sim (2008) looked into how much ICT was used by secondary school instructors. They discovered that more experienced educators than novice ones routinely incorporated instructional technology into their lessons.

Senior teachers find it easier to incorporate and integrate educational technology into their work when they have both teaching experience and rudimentary ICT skills. According to Lawless and Pellegrino (2007), teacher education programs that emphasize ICT skills and creative teaching methods can help teachers adapt and integrate ICT in the classroom. The training term should last long enough to provide the trainee teacher enough experience to become confident using technology in the classroom. Thus, the primary goal of the research was to identify the variables that affect teachers' motivation to incorporate ICT into the classroom. It looks at the individual experiences, educational environment, and technological aspects of teaching that led instructors to embrace and employ ICT in teaching.

Benefits of ICT in education:

Adoption of ICT boost learning effectiveness, lessen the workload for educators, make information sharing easier, inspire students more, and help students' IT proficiency. ICT enables the use of cutting-edge teaching strategies and educational tools to foster more active student collaboration while also obtaining technical expertise.

Early childhood education, benefits from the use of information and communication technology, because it allows kids to explore, observe, engage, solve issues, and make fascinating discoveries. Quick feedback is given to pupils through integrated ICT assessment. Technology- based assessment gives them feedback on their learning, which increases their confidence. Greater student engagement and participation in the classroom is one of the main advantage of ICT training for educators.

Technology enables educators to design more dynamic and engaging classes that grab students' interest and hold it throughout the lesson. Educational technology offers numerous benefits to the pupils. Learning-disabled individuals can use educational technology to help them with some of their challenges. Even math-phobic students can become more engaged in the topic and perform better in class as a whole.

Technology's primary contribution to education is to facilitate, excite, and enjoy learning. Students' knowledge and abilities are improved as a result of the advancement of technology in education. Technology-based learning not only improved academic performance but also gives students the freedom to study more from a variety of sources without relying on teachers.

The advent of technology has had significantly improved the level of communication and cooperation. It's a great way to prepare children for the future. Students can overcome difficulties and make better use of their skills.

Need and objective of the research:

The main objective of the study is to find out to what extent the selected variables, own experience, school environment and technical factors influenced the tendency of teachers to adopt and use ICT in teaching. The importance of internet in the life of every person is huge. The technological boom is also affecting the education sector. School management should be smart enough to implement ICT to support teaching and learning of teachers in the classroom, the importance of ICT in our daily life and education system is constantly increasing.

Therefore, there is a huge need in educational institutions to teach students the skills and knowledge needed in the 21st century with the help of information technology. To understand the impact of ICT on teaching and learning, today's educational institutions are trying to reform their curriculum and classrooms to bridge the technological gaps between teaching and learning. This restructuring process requires the effective application of technologies in the existing environment to inform students about certain subjects, promote meaningful learning and increase productivity (Tomei, 2005).

Objectives:

- A. Provides a conceptual framework for ICT in teaching and learning.
- B. To present the results of a study that examined the factors that influence the adoption of technology into teaching and learning.
- C. This study aims to identify the effectiveness of ICT integration from teaching and learning perspectives.
- D. To identify the effective elements of ICT integration in teaching in private schools in Chennai..

The Conceptual Framework:

The research environment was defined and adapted as a conceptual framework. The technological acceptance model (TAM) of Davis Roger's theory is presented as a process where innovations are brought into the educational system through certain channels and overtime. The process of "decision making starts with the first channel" knowledge", which represents the ability of the decision – making unit of ICT users to integrate the technology, and ends with the "confirmation" of the users that they accept and adopt the technology.

The TAM theory consists of different components that represent the ICT adoption process of users, including: behavioural intentions, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use. While perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which a person believes that the benefits of using a particular technology will improve work performance, perceived ease of use refers to the importance of the technology's user-friendliness.

In general, TAM theory was developed to measure the efficiency or success of a technology, which helps to understand the value and effectiveness of a given system. It is also considered one of the most influential theories in the study of information systems today. However, this

theory has evolved over the years, adding more specific variables that explain how a user can adopt a technology.

Many factors that are directly related to the main objective of the study are included in the proposed framework, which explains how knowledge and perfection affect the usefulness and ease of use of ICT integration.

The factors included in the conceptual framework are carefully related to each other, so that the relationship between them measures their effectiveness in the integration of teachers of information and communication technology. However, teachers’ intention to adopt ICT is the most important variable that supports the key elements of the framework, such as ease of use, functionality, flexibility, availability and integration. In addition, teachers’ intention to use technology is strongly influenced by their perception of the usefulness of the system and perceived ease of use and determines their actual use of ICT. The framework motivated this research to examine the factors influencing teachers’ technology integration.

Methodology:

The methodology followed for carrying out the present study comprises the description of research design, questionnaire design, sampling design, methods of data collection, the application of statistical tools for analysing the data, etc.

Table1 : Methodology

Type of research conducted	Descriptive and Exploratory type of research
Approach of research followed	Combination of Qualitative and Quantitative Approach of research
Population and sampling Unit of research	Private school teachers in Chennai of Tamil Nadu state
Sample size	250 private school teachers in Chennai as a pilot study
Study Area	Chennai, Tamil Nadu
Method/Technique of Sampling	Purposive Sampling(Non-Probability Sampling)

Type of data collected	Primary data (Majority)and Secondary data
Sources of Primary Data	Questionnaire and Personal Interview
Sources of Secondary Data	Research Articles, Magazines, Reports, Newspapers, Journals, Books, Online sources
Research Instrument used	Structured Questionnaire
Data collection period	August 2023 to September 2023
Software employed for data feeding and analysis	Microsoft Word and Excel 2016 and SPSS (Ver.20)

Source: Prepared by the Researcher.

Research Design:

This study first used a quantitative data collection methodology and analyse data obtained from all the respondents. The questionnaire was prepared and finalized and given before distribution to the target group. Few sections in the questionnaire was designed specifically to address research objectives in regard with the effectiveness of ICT integration for students in learning and effective elements of ICT integration in private schools in Chennai.

Population and Sampling:

Respondents of this study were 250 primary school teachers from private schools in Chennai as a pilot study. The questionnaire was randomly distributed to respondents with a teaching background, regardless of gender, race, teaching experience and practical knowledge. There are no preferences set by the researcher as long as the respondents come with teaching background, especially in private schools Chennai from primary, secondary and higher secondary segments. Since the targeted respondents for this research was with regard to the teaching background, the researcher tried to get especially teachers from private schools of Chennai, as the collection of data would be easy.

This study used a survey questionnaire containing a total of 40 aspects as the main instrument to analyse the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching and learning in private schools in Chennai.

A total of 250 questionnaires were distributed, where all respondents were asked to read the given statements and choose answers. A 4-part survey using a 5-point Likert scale to gather main data from the respondents was used. The 5-point Likert scale provides a straightforward way to interpret responses due to its ordinal nature, where each point represents a degree of agreement or disagreement.

The questionnaire consists of 4 parts. Part A: This is the demographic background of the respondents, consisting of six aspects of gender, teaching experience, school type, school

district, teaching style habits, highest academic qualifications and ability to use ICT in teaching.

The next three parts of the study focus more on teachers' perceptions and elements of the effectiveness of ICT integration in school. Part B: This part contains 15 aspects of how teachers seed ICT in teaching. Part C: This part contains 10 aspects of the effectiveness of ICT integration in students' learning. Part D: This part contains 10 aspects of the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching. The questionnaire used in this quantitative study was adopted and modified from the original questionnaire by Gulbar and Guven (2008) and was considered suitable for this study.

Some of the elements were designed and developed by the researcher according to the chosen title, so that the developed elements provide the necessary answers to both research questions.

Data analysis tools and results:

All the data received from the respondents were collected for analysis using STATISTICAL PACKAGE FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES (SPSS). IBM SPSS Statistics 20 is a sophisticated piece of software used by social scientists and related professionals for statistical analysis. The analysis includes both descriptive and inferential.

Descriptive analysis was used to analyse the frequency and proportion of the total population by demographic background. It is also used to determine mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage to determine the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching and learning.

Results:

The findings of this research will give the output needed by the researchers to answer the research questions. The findings are done as per the sections in the questionnaire and some inferential analysis that includes reliability testing and t-Test towards overall data.

Table 1. Demographic background of respondents

Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	45	82%
Female	205	18%
Teaching Experience		
<1 yr	40	16%
1-5 yrs	100	40%
6-10 yrs	85	34%
>10 yrs	25	10%
Type of School		
Primary	76	30.4%
Secondary	150	60%
Higher Secondary	24	9.6%
Preference of Teaching style		
Conventional/Tradition	55	22%
Modern/Contemporary	195	78%

(Use of ICT)		
Highest Academic Qualification		
Diploma	30	12%
Degree	120	48%
Post Graduation	85	34%
Technical	15	6%
The Ability of Handling ICT in Teaching		
High	63	25%
Medium	162	64.8%
Low	25	10%

From the total respondents (n=250), by gender, there are 205 female respondents with a share of 82%, while there are only45, male respondents with a share of 18%. Based on the teaching experience of the entire population, the majority of the respondents have 1-5 years of teaching experience, 40% respondents have 6-10 years of teaching experience, 16% have less than 1 year of teaching experience, and 10% of the respondents have more than 10 years of teaching experience. Of all the respondents 60% are from high school, 30.4% from primary school and 9.6% from high school. Of all the total respondents, 78% of the respondents prefer modern type of teaching style which favours the use of ICT and 22% of the respondents prefer traditional teaching style. Of all the respondents, 48% have master’s degree as their highest academic qualification, 34% have a diploma, 12% have a higher qualification and 6% have a technical qualification. Of all the respondents 64.8% of the respondents have an average skill in dealing with ICT in teaching, 25% of the respondents have good ICT in teaching, and 10% have a weak skill in dealing with ICT in teaching.

Table 2: Teacher’s perception of ICT integration in teaching

S. no	Items	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	S.d
		Frequency					
1.	I feel confident learning new computer skills.	0	10	200	40	1.88	1.35
2.	I find it easier to teach by using ICT.	0	22	175	53	1.87	1.38
3.	I think that ICT supported teaching makes learning more effective.	2	25	150	73	1.82	1.37
4.	I am aware of the great opportunities that ICT offers for effective teaching.	4	15	175	56	1.87	1.39

5.	The use of ICT helps teachers to improve teaching with more updated materials.	4	20	126	100	1.71	1.30
6.	I think the adoption of ICT helps to prepare teaching resources and materials.	2	15	105	128	1.65	1.19
7.	I think the integration of ICT improves the quality of "teaching.	2	10	175	63	1.80	1.37
8.	The use of ICT enables the students' to be more active and involved in the lesson.	0	12	200	38	1.89	1.37
9.	I have more time to cater to students' need if ICT is used in teaching.	0	25	210	15	2.04	1.50
10	I can still have an effective teaching without the use of ICT	50	100	75	25	2.70	2.32
11	I think the use of ICT in teaching is a waste of time.	40	175	20	15	2.96	2.50
12	The classroom management is out of control if ICT is used in teaching.	95	65	60	30	2.90	2.55
13	Students pay less attention when ICT is used in teaching.	50	155	40	5	3.0	2.52
14	I am confident that my students learn best without the help of ICT.	50	150	40	10	2.96	2.51
15	Students make no effort For their lesson if ICT is used in teaching.	100	125	20	5	3.28	2.82

The information presented in Table 2 on teachers' perceptions of adopting ICT in teaching shows that majority of the teachers are more aware of the usefulness and good effects of ICT in teaching. Most of the teachers understood that using of ICT helps to prepare learning materials and resources, with the lowest mean of 1.65, indicating that most of the teachers feel confident in learning new computer skills and can use ICT to find learning materials and resources.

In this study, it shows that teachers are more open and interested to use ICT in teaching, not against it, and also feel comfortable and interested to learn new things. Most of the teachers observed that the use of ICT helps and enhances teachers to improve their teaching methodology with the help of latest materials with an average of 1.71 which proves that the

resources and materials offered in online are up-to-date and teachers can refer them to prepare more valuable and engaging lessons for students.

In addition, many teachers believe that the use of information and communication technology increases the quality of teaching, the average of which was 1.80, which means that the majority of teachers accept and are interested in the use of ICT in their teaching. Next, the data show that the majority of teachers believe that teaching with ICT support improves learning with an average of 1.82. This shows that teachers are more open to integrating ICT skills in teaching methodology.

It also shows that ICT integration facilitates teaching with an average of 1.87 and teachers are confident of acquiring new computer skills with an average of 1.88. This clearly indicates that most of the teachers feel confident in learning the integration of computer skills and are able to use ICT to find different teaching materials and resources for better teaching methodologies and pedagogies.

On the other hand, few teachers do not agree that ICT enables them to meet the needs of their students. Some teachers believe that teaching can be carried out effectively without using information and communication technology with an average of 2.70 because the use of ICT disturbs the students' concentration on the subject while teaching.

However, some teachers with an average score of 2.96 think that the adoption of ICT in teaching is waste of time and concentration affects, followed by an average of 3.0 students who pay less attention to the use of ICT in teaching and most of the teachers were from the opinion that the use of ICT in teaching does not make an effort in their classes, which shows that the teacher is less accepting of ICT integration because the student is too involved and dependent on ICT and does not take responsibility for independent learning, which frustrates and disappoints teachers.

Table 3: Effectiveness of ICT integration for student's learning

S.NO	ITEMS	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	MEAN	S.D
		Frequency and percentage(%)					
	ICT allows students' to be more creative and imaginative	0	10	200	40	1.88	1.356466
2	The use of ICT helps students to find related knowledge and information for learning.	0	22	175	53	1.876	1.3885244
3	The use of ICT encourages students to communicate more with their classmates	2	20	180	50	1.912	1.41985915
4	The use of ICT increases students' confidence to participate actively in the class	4	15	175	56	1.868	1.39713994
5	I think students learn more effectively with the use of ICT	2	10	175	63	1.804	1.31757353
6	I think the use of ICT helps to broaden students' knowledge paradigm	2	10	200	38	1.904	1.39140217
7	I think the use of ICT helps to improve students' ability specifically in reading and writing	5	15	180	50	1.9	1.42828569
8	The students' are more behaved and under control with the use of ICT	5	15	190	40	1.94	1.45602198
9	The use of ICT enables students' to express their ideas and thoughts better	5	15	180	50	1.9	1.42828569
10	The use of ICT promotes active and engaging lesson for students' best learning experience	0	10	200	40	1.88	1.356466

The results obtained from Table 3 which examines the effectiveness of ICT integration for students in learning shows that students learn more effectively with the use of ICT as best learning experience with a record of lowest mean score of 1.804. In table 2, most teachers agreed that the adoption of ICT helps students to be more active and involved in the lesson. This shows that both teachers and students agreed that the use of ICT increases the chances of being more active and participative in learning methodologies.

The use of ICT increases students' confidence to participate actively in the class with the mean score of 1.86 . It also helps the students to find related knowledge and information for learning with a mean score of 1.87 and also helps students to be more creative and imaginative and also the use of ICT promotes active and engaging lesson for students' best learning experience, both with a mean score of 1.88.

On the other hand the use of ICT enables students to express their ideas and thoughts better and helps to broaden students' ability of reading and writing and also broadens their knowledge paradigm with a mean score of 1.90.

The results shows that the effectiveness of ICT for students in learning encourages them to communicate more with their classmates in sharing and exchanging their opinion with other students. Finally it shows that students are more behaved and under control with the use of ICT in learning, but also considered as little accepted by teachers as the mean is highest of all with a score of 1.94. This may imply to the teachers that students are a bit out of control with ICT integration in teaching, as teacher is not the main focus in learning process.

Table 4: Effective elements in ICT integration in teaching and learning in Schools

S.NO	ITEMS	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	MEAN	S.D
		Frequency and percentage(%)					
1	The ICT facilities in my school are well-functioning and can be used	60	120	50	20	2.88	2.48193473
2	The technical supports are provided if teachers are faced with difficulties	30	120	60	40	2.56	2.19089023
3	Little access to ICT prevents me from using it in teaching	15	45	135	55	2.08	1.69705627
4	Lack of support from the school top management discourages me from using ICT	10	25	155	60	1.94	1.52315462
5	Teaching time is not enough for me to use the ICT for teaching and learning purposes	5	40	150	55	1.98	1.54919334
6	There is enough training and professional development provided for the teachers about ICT use in teaching	20	115	65	50	2.42	2.05912603
7	All ICT tools in my school go to waste and less used by teachers	10	40	120	80	1.92	1.54919334
8	Teachers are given more time to learn and be comfortable with the use of ICT in teaching	40	160	40	10	2.92	2.4657656
9	There is computer lab in my school in which I can bring students to watch educational videos	40	130	60	20	2.76	2.34946802
10	Teachers are given the freedom to design their own teaching with the help of the ICT	15	110	100	10	2.4	2.03960781

From the data obtained it shows that teachers feel that all ICT tools go to waste and less used by teachers for the learning purpose with a mean score of 1.92 and lack of support from the school management from using ICT with a mean score of 1.94, so the teaching time is not enough for the teacher to use ICT for teaching and learning process with a mean score of 1.98. It is good if teachers are given more time and access to the integration of ICT in their lessons. Sometimes, ICT facilities are completely provided, but little access to ICT prevents teachers from using it in teaching process with a mean score of 2.08.

Besides, teachers feel, if they are given freedom to design their own teaching with the help from the use of ICT with a score of 2.40 and if enough training and professional development is provided about the usage of ICT in teaching and learning process would be more effective with a mean score of 2.42. School should provide technical support to the teachers if they face the difficulties with a mean score of 2.56.

Some schools are not provided with proper computer labs where students can watch educational videos for better learning and understanding with a mean score of 2.76. On the other hand ICT facilities provided in school are not well functioning and not in good condition as it is not being used properly with a mean of 2.88 and there is no proper maintenance of the ICT facilities by the school management.

Finally, the worst findings show that teachers are not given enough time to learn and be comfortable with the use and integration of ICT in teaching process with the highest mean score of 2.92. Hence it is better if teachers are provided with sufficient time to learn and integrate ICT with their teaching methodologies, so that learning process would be effective. The overall findings shows that the effective elements identified to be taken care by the schools for effective integration of ICT in teaching and learning process.

Reliability testing:

The Cronbach's Alpha reliability testing is used to test the internal consistency of an instrument and its items. It is considered as a measurement for scale reliability. For this study, the scale used is 5-point Likert scale ranged from 5=Neutral, 4=strongly disagree, 3=disagree, 2=agree, 1=strongly agree. As none of the respondents opted neutral it is ignored.

According to Kline (1999) the most accepted value of alpha value is something greater than 0.7. For this research, reliability test is done accordingly by part that includes part B, C and D of the questionnaire.

Table 5: The Reliability test for teacher's perception of ICT integration in teaching

S.No	Items	Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
1	I feel confident learning new computer skills.	0.18	0.97	15
2	I find it easier to teach by using ICT.	0.28		
3	I think that ICT supported teaching makes learning more effective.	0.39		
4	I am aware of the great opportunities that ICT offers for effective teaching.	0.33		
5	The use of ICT helps teachers to improve teaching with more updated materials.	0.46		
6	I think the adoption of ICT helps to prepare teaching resources and materials.	0.41		

7	I think the integration of ICT improves the quality of "teaching.	0.28
8	The use of ICT enables the students' to be more active and involved in the lesson.	0.18
9	I have more time to cater to students' need if ICT is used in teaching.	0.15
10	I can still have an effective teaching without the use of ICT	0.81
11	I think the use of ICT in teaching is a waste of time.	0.48
12	The classroom management is out of control if ICT is used in teaching.	1.09
13	Students pay less attention when ICT is used in teaching.	0.44
14	I am confident that my students learn best without the help of ICT.	0.52
15	Students make no effort For their lesson if ICT is used in teaching.	0.48

The reliability test shows the result of alpha value as 0.97 which means that the items are acceptable and it can be considered as an instrument for the respondents.

Table 6: The reliability test for effectiveness of ICT integration for student's learning

S.No	Items	Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
1	ICT allows students' to be more creative and imaginative	0.18	0.98	10
2	The use of ICT helps students to find related knowledge and information for learning.	0.28		
3	The use of ICT encourages students to communicate more with their classmates	0.29		
4	The use of ICT increases students' confidence to participate actively in the class	0.33		
5	I think students learn more effectively with the use of ICT	0.28		
6	I think the use of ICT helps to broaden students'knowledge paradigm	0.21		
7	Ithink the use of ICT helps to improve students' ability specifically in reading and writing	0.33		
8	The students' are more behaved and under control with the use of ICT	0.29		

9	The use of ICT enables students' to express their ideas and thoughts better	0.33
10	The use of ICT promotes active and engaging lesson for students' best learning experience	0.18

The reliability test for the effectiveness of ICT integration in learning for students shows that the result of alpha value is more than 0.98 which is good and satisfactory reliability of the items as research instruments to the respondents.

Table 7: The reliability test for the effective elements in ICT integration in teaching and learning in Schools

S.No	Items	Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
1	The ICT facilities in my school are well-functioning and can be used	0.74	0.96	10
2	The technical supports are provided if teachers are faced with difficulties	0.8		
3	Little access to ICT prevents me from using it in teaching	0.63		
4	Lack of support from the school top management discourages me from using ICT	0.49		
5	Teaching time is not enough for me to use the ICT for teaching and learning purposes	0.46		
6	There is enough training and professional development provided for the teachers about ICT use in teaching	0.8		
7	All ICT tools in my school go to waste and less used by teachers	0.63		
8	Teachers are given more time to learn and be comfortable with the use of ICT in teaching	0.47		
9	There is computer lab in my school in which I can bring students to watch educational videos	0.66		
10	Teachers are given the freedom to design their own teaching with the help of the ICT	0.77		

The reliability test for the effective elements in ICT integration in teaching and learning in schools shows that the result of alpha value is greater than 0.96 which means that the items are acceptable and can be considered as an instrument for the respondents.

Hypothesis testing:

Independent Sample “t” Test - Analysis

H01: There is no significant difference between teachers’ perception of ICT in teaching with the type of school (Primary & Secondary)

Item	Mean	SD	SEM	t	p
Table 2	2.28	0.6	0.03	2.17	0.03 **
Table 4	2.38	0.38	0.02		

**** Significant P<0.05**

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare the difference between the Primary and Secondary school teachers with respect to the acceptance of ICT integration in the regular teaching with the effective elements in ICT integration in teaching and learning in schools. (P value =0.03) which is statistically significant and says if ICT facilities in school are well equipped and teachers are trained and supported from the management, both primary and secondary teachers can use them effectively. Hence, hypothesis is accepted.

H02: There is no significant difference between the effectiveness of ICT integration for students in learning with the teaching experience.

Item	Mean	SD	SEM	t	p
Table 2	2.28	0.6	0.03	10.7	0.0001 **
Table 3	1.88	0.041	0.002		

**** Significant P<0.05**

An independent-sample t-test was conducted between the effectiveness of ICT integration for students in learning with the teaching experience. (p<0.0001) which is extremely statistically significant and says if effectiveness of ICT integration for students learning is taken care, teaching experience of teachers will not matter. Hence, hypothesis is accepted.

H03: Adoption of ICT and handling of ICT has a positive relationship with proper training and digital capabilities to handle.

Item	Mean	SD	SEM	t	p
Table 3	1.88	0.04	0.002	20.6	0.0001 **
Table 4	2.38	0.38	0.02		

**** Significant P<0.05**

An independent-sample t-test was conducted for adoption of ICT with proper training and digital capabilities to handle. ($p < 0.0001$) which is extremely statistically significant and says with the proper digital capabilities and training, adoption of ICT has a positive relationship. Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Findings and Suggestions:

The results of this study show that technology-based teaching and learning is more effective in compared to traditional classroom. This is because, using ICT tools and equipments will prepare an active learning environment that is more interesting and effective for both teachers and students. The results are in line with a research findings by Macho (2005) that proved using ICT in education would enhance students' learning. However, most of teachers in this study agree that ICT helps to improve classroom management as students are well-behaved and more focussed. Moreover, this study proved that students learn more effectively with the use of ICT as lessons designed are more engaging and interesting. Accordingly, the participants agreed that integrating ICT can foster students' learning.

It might be too common for issues and challenges of ICT integration to be discussed , but in depth study of ICT integration in core subjects is least discussed. It is good if further studies can be made based on what barriers teachers are facing in using ICT in their daily classrooms in schools. Besides, rather than just focussing in private schools , it is best if this study can be conducted in public schools and international schools, because , some schools might have more funding that makes ICT implementation much faster and easier. It is highly recommended for comparative study about ICT integration in teaching and learning to be done between public and private schools.

Conclusion:

The adoption of ICT skills among educators is more than just a technological shift; it is a transformative process that has the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning in the 21st century. By leveraging technology effectively, educators can create dynamic, interactive, and personalized learning environments that engage students, foster critical thinking skills, and prepare them for success in a digital-driven world. In conclusion, the first stage of ICT implementation must be effective, so that teachers and the students can get the most benefit out of it. Preparation for technology-based teaching and learning thus begins with proper implementation and support from the school's top management. If the tools and equipment are proper and implementation goes well from the beginning and adequate care is taken for ongoing maintenance, the adoption and integration of ICT in the schools will bring great success and benefits for both teachers and students.

Therefore, the main objective of the study is to find out the factors that influence the motivation and interest of teachers to adopt ICT in the classroom. It explores teachers 'personal experiences, school environment and technical factors that influenced their motivation to adopt and integrate and use ICT in teaching and learning. Thus, preparations of a technology-based teaching and learning begin with proper implementation and supports by

the school top management. Finally, the integration of ICT in classrooms need serious consideration in order to increase the competency of education system. In order to enhance the use of ICT in classroom the management and the government needs to improve and change the teachers' belief of ICT integration in classroom. The proposed framework has guided this research in investigating the factors affecting the technology integration by school teachers.

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